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Impact Of Science-Process Approach On Secondary School Students' Interest, Performance And Retention On Practical Chemistry In Taraba State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the Impact of Science-Process Approach on Secondary School Students' Interest, Performance and Retention on Practical Chemistry in Taraba State, Nigeria. The area of the study is Karim-Lamido LGA. This research adopted a quasi-experimental research design involving pretest, posttest and post-posttest control group design. three research question and three null hypotheses were formulated, three Instruments Science Process Approach Rating Scale (SPARS), Practical Chemistry Performance Test (PCPT) and Student Chemistry Interest Test (SCIT) were subjected to content and face validation. The reliability of the instrument was established using Alpha Cronbach and reliability coefficient of the three instruments at 0.85 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question while analysis of covariance and t-test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. From the analysis, it was revealed that Performance, Interest and Retention scores of students taught practical chemistry using Science Process Approach was higher than those taught using the Alternative to Practical Method. There was no significant difference in the mean Performance, Interest and Retention scores of both Male and Female as such science process Approach is gender friendly. It is evident from this study that the use of science process Approach could enhance student's performance in practical chemistry. It is recommended based on the findings of this study that: chemistry teachers should be encourage to adopt science process Approach method while teaching practical chemistry, workshops and seminars should be organized for chemistry teachers to motivate them incorporate new teaching strategy like science process Approach in the teaching and learning of practical chemistry.

Keywords: Science Process Approach, Secondary School, Interest, Performance, Retention, Practical Chemistry and Students.

INTRODUCTION

Science education exposes learners to the contents as well as the methodology (processes) of acquiring scientific knowledge for practical application in relevant areas of life endeavors (Jaksh, 2022). It makes efficient provision of preparation for citizens which have been observed to be possible when there is provision of scientifically literate teacher who have the idea of the global needs for teaching with the aim of instilling scientific and technological values in learner. It is therefore good news that an average individual with sufficient amount of chemistry background coupled with a sound idea with interest can become job creators rather than job seekers.

Knowledge of science can be acquired through science education. Science education is the application of principles of education in the development and acquisition of processes/procedures required to help others acquire scientific and technological knowledge for ready application to everyday living. One of

the important science subjects that its knowledge if acquired can be applied in everyday living is Chemistry (Jack and Ndong, 2022).

In today 's modern era, education is a very important. This is because humans need education to be useful for society and the nation, thereby producing an intellectual generation to increase knowledge. National education functions to develop spiritual, social, knowledge and skills abilities, this development reflect the benefits derived from improving education. Therefore, to improve the quality of education, it is done through a focus on teaching (Ernawati et al., 2022). Effective methods of teaching, especially in the sciences can create a robust economy which can stem the problem of unemployment.

Science and technology have been identified as important factors of socio-economic development, showing the need to develop and channel our curriculum towards skills acquisition (Efe & Abamba, 2023). The educational state of any nation remains the major determinant of its development in all ramifications. The values of liberal education such as curiosity, honesty, open-mindedness, objectivity, and pursuit of truth are regular characteristics of the teaching of science. These values, when built into the teaching and learning of science, will create room for the acquisition of necessary skills. A nation cannot develop without giving proper attention to science education (Akanbi & Omoniye, 2024).

Chemistry is the subdivision of science that deals with the identification and transformation of the constituents of which material is composed, an experimental science that systematically studies the composition, properties, and activities of organic and inorganic substances and various elementary forms of matter (Aimable et al., 2023). Chemistry at the secondary school level is expected to be taught as a process of inquiry developing in students' cognitive skills, affective skills and psychomotor skills of science. This is however very important because the three educational domains are captured in the teaching and learning process which will bring a more balanced outcome to the learner and the society at large as stated in the National Policy on Education. As a result, teachers ought to focus on developing scientific abilities, including science processes skills, in order to address issues such as global environmental change, food security, and safeguarding of clean water.

For students to fully develop scientific skills in the twenty-first century, science process skills (SPS) become a prerequisite (Bete, 2020). Given the significance of chemistry education, chemistry curricula in many countries emphasises the importance for students to engage in the acquisition of knowledge and scientific skills, particularly SPS (Aydm, 2013; Abungu et al., 2014; Bete, 2020). As a science subject, chemistry needs a constant stream of practical or hands-on activities to explain abstract ideas and inculcate relevant scientific skills required for problem solving (Kinyota, 2020). Therefore, practical works or hands-on activities are the most essential learning technique which allow students to discover scientific facts and concepts

Furthermore, practical works are more interesting than lectures in the classroom—they provide an opportunity for students to collaborate and engage with one another and their teachers; and enhance their sense of ownership of their learning (Flavia, 2022). An innovation in Chemistry lessons would enable the objectives of the Chemistry curriculum become achievable. There are different methods teachers can use to teach Chemistry one of which is the Science Process Approach. Science Process Approach is a teaching strategy that exposes the learners to diverse science process skills. Process science (or a "process approach") refers to science courses or programs that emphasize the development of students' "science process skills," that is, their ability to use the "processes of science" in carrying out tasks. These are considered to be the processes which scientists follow when exploring the natural world and developing scientific explanations. There is no complete agreement among science educators on what the specific processes of science are. Most lists of processes however include observing, measuring, classifying, inferring, predicting, hypothesizing, and finding patterns, and some also add: experimenting, planning investigations, controlling variables, communicating, and others. A "process approach" to science contrasts with the more usual "content approach," in which the development of students' practical and inquiry skills is seen as secondary to, or a by-product of the development of their scientific knowledge and understanding of process skills.

Chemistry practical skills are science process skills. They are taught as part and parcel of the chemistry curriculum. Science process skills are cognitive and psycho-motor skills employed in problem solving. (Jack 2018) opined that science process skills are reasoning abilities which are used by scientists to solve problems, and that the process approach to teaching science is meant to foster inquiry and manipulative skills in students and discourage rote learning. Science process skills are

special skills that learners and teachers use in carrying out mental operation of and physical activities in the field of science. It is an attempt to make students fully aware as well as understand the ways scientists work and the need to be equipped and prepared with possible careers in science and technology. The significance of the science process skills has led to the expansion of the goals of science education to include an understanding by and development in the students of these process skills (Flavia et al., 2022).

The development of science process skills as opined by Jack (2018) is a very important object of instruction, this is because scientists use them to design and implement procedures for problem solving. Chemistry as a branch of science can be taught and learned most effectively if Chemistry is practical supported. Chemistry laboratory is a building equipped with Chemistry apparatus for carrying out experiments. Laboratory experiments are characteristics features of science teaching at all levels of education. Students have a lot to benefit from practical work which may include increasing students' interest and abilities as well as their performance in Chemistry (Tsobaza, 2023). The low interest of students in Chemistry reflects on their performance in both internal and external Examination.

Alternative to Practical paper is simply an alternative mode of assessment to the Practical Examination paper. It requires the same kind of practical work in preparation as the Practical Examination paper (Cambridge International Examinations, 2016). Alternative to Practical paper assesses students' practical skills, including both data handling and familiarity with standard laboratory equipment. Any candidates without experience of doing practical work will be disadvantaged in this paper. In addition, students without practical knowledge will not be able to perform well in the alternative to practical paper or examination. Most teachers usually adopt this approach for chemistry practical activities due to scarcity of chemicals and laboratory equipment's.

Performance is an important academic factor which is a measurable change in students' behaviors that is influenced by teaching strategies. Muhammed (2020) sees performance as the process of getting something done effectively and successfully using effort and skills aimed at accomplishment of academic goals. According to Narad and Abdullah (2016), academic performance is the knowledge gained which is assessed by marks by a teacher and/or educational goals set by students and teachers to be achieved over a specific period of time. When students perform well in a given task, there is that tendency that the knowledge they have gained is retained in their memories. The knowledge retention of concepts as opined by Philip (2013) is the ability to remember facts and other information. Concept retention is the ability to remember fundamental concepts rather than "just" facts. Students should not only remember the scales of measurement for example, but should be able to measure objects in real life. Retention is an ability to recall or recognize what has been learned or experienced; or the course of absorbing information and eventually retaining the information overtime. Performance can be influence by the student interest in specific subject.

Interest is a desire, and can be considered as a person's liking for something. Interest is one aspect that affects student performance; therefore, interest needs to be developed (Tambunan et al., 2021). Interest can be developed with interesting learning so that students' enthusiasm will arise for the learning process that takes place. The science learning process taken by students will run well and as expected if students have a high interest in learning Interest in student learning, of course, apart from arising from each individual, can be spurred by the encouragement and direction of a teacher. The low interest of students in Chemistry reflects on their performance in both internal and external Examination. According to Tsobaza (2023), the West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiner's Report for senior secondary certificate examination for the year 2018-2024 identified that one of the reasons for poor performance and low interest of students in Chemistry is teachers teaching method and students inadequate exposure to (practical) laboratory work and poor preparation.

Statement Of The Problem

Chemistry has a crucial role in the rapid developments in science and technology. In spite of this, Chemistry is taught in most secondary schools in abstract without Practical experiences. Lack of practical chemistry has resulted to students' low acquisition of science process instruction which have become more evident in the mass failure of students in the chemistry subject in secondary certificate examinations like National Examination Council (NECO) and West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and lack of interest on the subject as many students shy away from the course and prefer to study other courses at higher institution. For instance, the WAEC Chief

examiners' report (2024) on Chemistry shows that students had the following weaknesses; Unable to distinguish between dehydrating agent, Inability to state the correct observation of simple experiments (e.g. precipitates were incorrectly described, and inferences stated did not correspond to observations recorded), Inability to outline how recrystallization is carried out in the laboratory. All the questions asked in the instruments to test chemistry Students' knowledge in Practical skills require that they demonstrate one form of process skill or the other. The inability of students to carry out these activities properly results in low scores in the test of Practical knowledge there by leading to the frequently observed rate of poor performance in chemistry and science as a whole. This can be shown evidently from the trend in WAEC results of students in Taraba State from 2019 to 2024. WAEC results from 2019-2024). It is on this note that the researcher strives to investigate the impact of science process instructions in enhancing students' interest, performance and retention in Practical chemistry in Karim-Lamido local government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria. The problem of the study therefore is, 'Will the use of science process approach helps in improving Secondary School Students' Interest, Performance and Retention in Practical Chemistry and Science Process Approach in Senior Secondary School in Karim-Lamido Local Government Area of Taraba State?'

Purpose of the Study

The study investigated the Impact of Science-Process Approach on Secondary School Students' Interest, Performance and Retention on Practical Chemistry in Karim-Lamido LGA of Taraba State, Nigeria, specifically, the study sought to find out:

- i. the difference in the performance of students taught practical chemistry using science process approach and those taught using the Alternative to practical method.

Research Question

One research question guided the study:

- i. what is the difference in the mean performance scores of students taught practical chemistry using the science process approach compared to those taught the same concepts using the Alternative to practical method?

Hypothesis

One null Hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance for the purpose of generalization

- i. H_{01} : There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of Students taught Practical chemistry using science process approach and their counterparts taught same concepts using the Alternative to practical method.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study is the pretest, posttest, posttest non-equivalent and control group quasi-experimental design. The treatment was administered to the students in the experimental and control groups after a pre-test, was done a week before the treatment commences in order to determine the group equivalent. After the pre-test, the students will be taught chemistry practical for a period of four weeks (treatment). The researcher will develop a Chemistry practical lesson plan for the experimental group using a Science Process Instruction and an Alternative to practical lesson plan for the control group. These lessons will be prepared based on quantitative and qualitative analysis contained in the recent senior secondary School education curriculum approved by the Nigerian Education Research Development Council (NERDC 2022) used in the teaching of Chemistry practical. At the end of the fourth week, the researcher will administer the instruments (SPARS), (PCPT) and (SCAT) in other to determine the interest and academic performance of the students in the experimental and control groups. After some two weeks, the researcher will administer the SPARS and PCPT to the EG and CG in other to determine the retention level of the students in these two groups.

In each of the selected schools, (Government Day Senior Secondary School Karim and Government Day Senior Secondary School Jen) experienced and qualified Chemistry teachers and laboratory technicians will be recruited and trained by the researcher for a period of one week before the commencement of the treatment. For the experimental group, four qualified Chemistry teachers will be recruited to assist in the practical this is because of the stress and hard work involved in controlling a large class during chemistry practical and proper rating of each student. These teachers will be trained on how to go about the Science Process instruction and alternative to practical approach. Science Process instruction refers to science pedagogy that emphasizes the development of students'

“science process instruction,” that is, their ability to use the “processes of science” in carrying out tasks. For the purpose of this study the students will be exposed to seven (7) science process instructions in which the students will be assessed. The seven science process instructions that the students will be assessed in this study include: observation, measurement, recording, communication, inference, controlling variables and experimentation. Objectives of the study and proper guidelines will be given to the research assistants including the lesson plans also reagents that will be used for the practical will be made available by the researchers. Such reagent are:

- i. Methyl Orange
- ii. Distle Water
- iii. $KMnO_4$ (Potassium Permanganate (v))
- iv. $FeSO_4$ (Iron II Sulphate)
- v. $FeCl_2$ (Iron II Chloride)
- vi. $NaOH_{(aq)}$ (Sodium Hydroxide) in Aqueous Solution
- vii. $NH_{3(aq)}$ (Ammonia)

Experimental Controls

During the study, the following Experimental variables were controlled;

Experimental Bias: During research certain distractions can occur some of which are distractions in behaviour which can arise especially when the participants in the study have the knowledge that they are subjects of study. When students are conscious of the fact that they are involved in an experimental work, that usually affect the students’ performance, (Hawthorne effect). In other to overcome this effect, the regular teachers of the two schools will be recruited as research assistants to coordinate the teaching and learning activity throughout the treatment period.

Experimental Contamination: To avoid experimental contamination, the research will be conducted in two different schools (Government Science Secondary School Jen and Government Day Secondary School Karim) that are far away from each other with same characteristics. This is to help the researcher in controlling the movement of students from one group to another.

Attrition: This refers to the loss of subject as a result of transfer or relocation, or dropping out of the experiment before it will be concluded. The researcher will control this extraneous variable by conducting the research within a short period of four weeks.

Effects of Pre-Test on Post-Test and retention test: The period between the pre-test and the post-test and post-posttest will be six weeks, which is the research period. The period is neither too long nor too short. This is to help cancel out the possible effects of the pre-test on the post-test and post-post-test. The pre-test questions will be reshuffled and restructured in different order before it can be administered as a post-test 4 weeks after treatment and post-posttest after another two weeks after posttest.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: *What is the difference in the mean performance scores of students taught practical chemistry using the Science Process Approach compared to those taught the same concepts using the Alternative to practical strategy?*

Table 1: Descriptive mean statistics on difference in the mean performance scores of students taught practical Chemistry using Science Process Approach and the students taught same concepts using the Alternative to Practical strategy.

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev	
SPA	50	20.18	5.97	42.54	4.57	22.36
APS	60	17.08	3.39	29.70	5.08	12.62

Results of table 1 shows that the posttest performance mean scores of students taught using Science Process Approach (SPA) is 42.54 with standard deviation of 4.57, while that of those taught using the Alternative to practical strategy (APS) is 29.70 with standard deviation of 5.08. The difference between the pretest and posttest performance mean scores of Science Process Approach is 22.36 and that of the Alternative to Practical is 12.62. This shows that the posttest mean scores are significantly higher than the pretest scores for both the two study groups especially among the Science Process

Approach. This therefore implies that students taught practical chemistry using the Science Process Approach performed better than their counterparts taught same concepts using the Alternative to Practical strategy.

CONCLUSION

In summary, implementing the Science Process Approach in practical chemistry education can transform the learning experience. It fosters greater student interest, improves their performance on assessments, and enhances their ability to retain and apply knowledge in the long run.

On the basis of the outcome of the study, it can be approximately concluded that the use of Science Process Approach is very effective for the teaching of practical chemistry in secondary schools and it is very gender friendly especially when this method is compared with the alternative to the practical strategy.

RECOMMENDATION

On the basis of this study the researchers recommended:

1. The use of Science Process Approach should be encouraged and recommended in all schools for the effective implementation of the practical chemistry curriculum by regular supervision and monitoring.

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